

Delinking Religious Prophecies of Destruction from the War on Gaza

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The Israeli-Palestinian conflict is often mischaracterized as a religious conflict, or a conflict between Muslims and Jews. This misperceived and inaccurate framing has contributed to its labeling as a deep-rooted and intractable conflict. When analysts, politicians, or others approach this conflict as one between the Jewish and Muslim faiths, various assumptions are made based on theological framing, perspectives, and values regarding the conflict's causes, processes, and possible resolutions.

However, in its origin and dynamics, the core of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict is about self-determination and national sovereignty over a specific territory. Its primary roots are in the Zionist movement claiming the land of historic Palestine in the late 1880s and ignoring the existence of Palestinian Arab inhabitants of that land. From a settler colonial perspective, it is very similar to what other Western colonial powers did during roughly the same period of history (the French in Algeria, the Dutch in South Africa, the Spanish and Filipino in Mindanao Philippines, etc.).

Throughout the history of the conflict between the settlers and indigenous people of the land, the religious identities of the two sides were deployed in order to justify territo-

rial and political claims for power and ownership. However, they have made these claims from two different starting points—one from settler colonialism, and the other from indigenous and locals struggling to survive a process backed by colonial superpowers.

Even before the 1948 *Nakba*, or the creation of the State of Israel, certain Jewish religious and theological interpretations were deployed to establish an exclusive ownership of the land and mobilize the migration of settlers from around the world and from specific religious communities. For example, as Don-Yehiya (2014) describes,

[I]n the pre-State period most religious Zionists were firmly opposed to any proposal for the partition of Palestine between Jews and Arabs. This attitude was clearly manifested in the debate at the 20th Zionist Congress in 1937 over the partition proposal of the British Palestine Royal Commission (the Peel Commission). The overwhelming majority of the religious Zionist representatives to the Congress voted against the proposal, and only a handful of the representatives abstained from the voting (244).

Similarly, the national Palestinian movement from its inception in the early 1900s, relied on religious identity markets to mobilize political and military resistance against the Zio-

nist Jewish settlers who were arriving in historic Palestine. For example, a quick and basic review of the narrative of the Palestinian revolt in 1936 against the British and Zionist colonial powers, provides ample evidence on how Islamic religious values and beliefs were deployed in the battles.

However, until about four decades ago, on both sides, the role of religious identities in the conflict, and in national political dynamics, remained confined to political minorities. The Palestinian resistance movement, led by the different factions of the Palestinian Liberation Organization (PLO), was dominated by a secular nationalist orientation until Hamas emerged in 1986. Similarly, on the Israeli Jewish side, the Jewish right wing religious settler ideology became more influential in the early 1980s, even dictating policies toward Palestinians and their quest for independence.

Today, during the war on Gaza, we have witnessed an even more dramatic shift in the rhetoric of Israeli government leaders. For example, in late October, Prime Minister Netanyahu referenced the Biblical attack of the Amalekites on the Israelites and invoked the story to justify the genocidal campaign against Palestinians in Gaza.

There is no doubt that there is a religious dimension to the Israeli Palestinian conflict—after all, it is the holy land, and it has all the history of the three Abrahamic faiths. Nevertheless, it is dangerous and destructive to mask the core issue of territorial conflict with zero-sum religious framing, or, even worse, to describe it as a conflict between ‘evil people’ versus ‘people of the light.’ It is even more dangerous to link the resolution and fight over territory with prophecies about a return of the Messiah or day of judgment.

Such linkages contribute to dehumanization and a sense of determinism that often lead to the escalation of the conflict and discourse of ‘total destruction of the other.’ It also feeds into a sense of hopelessness or helplessness in the capacities of people to reach mutually satisfactory resolutions. This can encourage submission to the belief that solutions to this conflict will only come about from a supernatural, or divine, intervention, and we all should simply wait for such a moment.

There is no doubt that, in our efforts to de-escalate and resolve this conflict, it is important to address the religious dimension by placing it in its proportional scale and context and preventing it from feeding into narratives of dehumanization and helplessness. Thus, political, religious extremism that mobilizes the hearts and minds of its followers need to be countered by religious narratives that promote diversity and inclusion, and acknowledge common religious values of justice, freedom, and dignity.

This does not mean that Western diplomats and policymakers should continue to totally ignore the religious dimensions of the conflict, as they have mostly done over the past century. Instead, politicians, diplomats and peace workers have to take into consideration and understand the religious actors and their impact on the conflict’s dynamics, and support efforts to counter the narratives of religious exclusivism that justify dehumanization, occupation, and apartheid systems. ♦

References

Don-Yehiya, Eliezer. 2014. “Messianism and Politics: The Ideological Transformation of Religious Zionism” *Israel Studies* 19(2): 239-263.